

The Protagonist's Quest or Journey Through Life in European Literature from Late Antiquity to the Early Modern Age: A Core Motif in European Culture

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Abstract

Certainly, there is currently a strong movement in the discourse on cultural history, sociology, anthropology, and literary studies to move ourselves away from a Eurocentric perspective and to open up global dimensions. Nevertheless, there is no doubt that Europe as a historical and cultural entity remains a unique phenomenon that deserves to be studied all by itself in clear contrast to Arabic, Persian, Indian, Chinese, African, or Latin-American literature, visual arts, philosophy, or music. Of course, Europe as a separate continent has always been determined by many different languages, social groups, religious sects and philosophical schools, and it has always been the recipient and a source of inspiration for many other cultures, but we can certainly identify a unifying core that determined and defined that continent from late antiquity until today, as contested this core or its definition might be. This study is not at all interested in demonstrating an alleged European superiority over other continents; instead, the purpose here is to isolate and determine a significant and shared motif characteristic of most European literature since the post-Roman period: the quest, and this in material and spiritual terms. This notion of the quest has probably always been a universal concept relevant for all people across the globe, but this paper only highlights the extent to which European literature since late antiquity has been deeply determined by the protagonist's desire for and need of reaching his/her goal in physical and spiritual terms, overcoming countless challenges, and accomplishing a unique task of supreme importance. We might deal here with an archetypal notion of global value, but a broad overview of some of the most important medieval and early modern narratives confirms that, indeed, the protagonist's quest can be identified as fundamentally important in European literature at least until modernity.

Keywords: *Pan-European literary motif; the hero's quest; courtly ideals; pilgrimage; the individual and society; medieval and early modern European literature.*

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Introduction

In their haste to live up to the ideals of decolonization, fighting against imperialism, racism, sexism, or misogyny, many younger cultural historians and literary scholars have tended to throw the proverbial baby out with the bathwater. We can only support the efforts to embrace a more global perspective in our humanist endeavors, to oppose narrow-minded imperialist concepts when we carry out analytic investigations, and to deconstruct traditional, patriarchal, and colonialist ideology. However, it would be an ill-conceived and hasty notion to dismiss in that process unique and certainly highly constructive features that have shaped European culture ever since the post-Roman period, and this in contrast to all other cultures in Asia, Africa, India, or Latin America.

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Of course, to state it bluntly from the start, while Europe experienced its own characteristic development throughout the ages and could, for quite a long time, impose a certain control over neighboring countries and even entire continents since the sixteenth and especially the eighteenth century, nothing would justify an intellectual or historical attempt to project Europe as superior, or inferior, compared to other cultures. Instead, to be fair and honest in that regard, throughout history, we observe constant competitions and military conflicts, and while some cultures seemed to dominate or supersede others for a shorter or longer period of time, there have never been automatic processes to cement or idealize any position in that long-term struggle for good.

Empires have come and empires have gone, but all kingdoms or nations have traditionally assumed a sense of superiority as the result of their natural desire to create a cultural identity in contrast to all other political entities. However, Orientalist viewpoints, for instance, the target of a heated and controversial discourse in the present, often excessively politicizing research, only emerged in the course of time, so we have to be rather careful in our assessment of this phenomenon as it developed in early modern and modern Europe. In short, we ought to discriminate much more carefully in that regard than Edward Said had done in his seminal study *Orientalism* in 1978 (cf. now Phillips 2013) to avoid the fallacy of a simplistic binary worldview.

History of Europe Within the Global Context

Early medieval Europe was truly nothing but *hinterland* compared to the Persian, Indian, Japanese, Chinese, or Arabic cultures and respective empires. It took hundreds of years for Europe to develop so much that it could assemble enough resources to embark on the Crusades (1096–1291). Ultimately, however, the Christian knights could not even hold their Latin kingdoms in the Eastern Mediterranean, and once the last fortress, Acre, had fallen in 1291, there were no more realistic opportunities for any European force to return to the Holy Land and recapture it from the Arabs for Christianity. Instead, European Christians could only go there on a pilgrimage or visit that part of the Eastern Mediterranean as merchants, diplomats, scholars, or political dignitaries. When the Mongols attacked Europe in the early thirteenth century, they did not stay long for a number of reasons, but in many respects, they regarded that continent as too poor and irrelevant for their efforts to build an empire on the Asian continent (Sechen 2023).

Seen from the opposite perspective, once the Ottoman forces under their Sultan Mehmed II had defeated and conquered Constantinople in 1453, they embarked on a long-term strategy to attack the Christian Balkans and then even threaten the Habsburg Empire, only to be defeated themselves in the course of time and then being pushed back throughout the following centuries, concluding with the defeat of the Ottomans at the end of World War I. Undoubtedly, the Turks initially commanded a better military discipline, strategy, morale, and also weaponry, which the European could at first not compete with. But both the Ottomans' failure in their effort to besiege Vienna in 1529 and again in 1683, and their defeat in the naval battle of Lepanto in 1571 clearly signaled that they had passed their zenith and from then on faced their nadir which they ultimately reached in 1918 having been defeated by the Allied forces (Seigel, 2025).

By contrast, several major events in late medieval Europe sparked a massive reorientation of that continent which laid the foundation of a global outreach from that continent, beginning with the invention of the movable type by Johannes Gutenberg in Mainz in ca. 1450, leading to a revolution in written communication, literature, and book production. This in turn had a huge impact on theology, philosophy, medicine, and the mechanical sciences. We can also attribute the strong development of firearms and innovative shipbuilding during the late Middle Ages as critical factor facilitating the subsequent explorations of foreign lands, especially the New World since Christopher Columbus had found the route across the Atlantic in 1492 and Vasco da Gama had learned how to sail around the Cape of Good Hope between 1497 and 1499 and thus to reach the Indian subcontinent. Italian bankers had developed new payment systems and financial transactions already since the fourteenth century, and since

the late fifteenth century, European mining took off, which subsequently triggered a profound paradigm shift in the production of weapons, tools, and other objects (*Methuen's History*, 1956–1967; Schorn-Schütte 2026; to be sure, the number of pertinent studies on all those aspects is legion).

Undoubtedly, the following centuries witnessed the rise of colonialism and imperialism, at the latest since the eighteenth century, but this did not promote and guarantee the European dominance forever, as the developments since the middle and late twentieth century have confirmed. And today, considering the complete shift in economic markets, with Japan and China, above all, dominating the rest of the world in many respects, with India, South Korea, and Brazil following closely behind both countries, we have learned to accept that the traditional Eurocentric perspective was rather limited (Burbank and Cooper 2010).

All world powers have experienced their ups and downs, whether we think of the Huns, the Avars, the Magyars, the Arabs, the Mongols, the Inkas or the Aztecs, and so forth. Europe as a whole has not been an exception in that regard, if we consider, for instance, the Carolingian Empire (eighth and ninth centuries) that did not last more than a few generations, or the fairly long-term rule of the Hohenstaufen dynasty in the twelfth and thirteenth centuries). The extensive period from the late Middle Ages until the twentieth century witnessed the rise and fall of various European superpowers, such as Spain, Portugal, France, Sweden, and England, but apart from the Ottomans, there were no serious challenges to the Continent throughout the early modern and modern age. However, we currently (ca. 2020–2026) face a dramatic shift once again because the new world powers prove to be the United States, China, and somewhat still Russia, all maybe soon to be replaced by India and Brazil. All we can say for sure is that no culture, no people, no continent has ever maintained continuous supremacy. All superpowers have eventually stumbled and then fallen at some point in time, whether we think of the Persians, the Babylonians, the Egyptians, the Greeks, the Romans, later the Spanish and Portuguese, the British, the French, and the Germans.

Nevertheless, it still proves to be a worthwhile effort to examine whether there might have been unique features, interests, concepts, notions, or attitudes, hence, in global terms, a broadly conceived mentality characterizing Europe prior to the twentieth century because it played such a central role all over the globe in the early modern history, both in terms of technology and sciences, medicine and economics (*C. H. Beck Geschichte Europas* 2010). Both World Wars have changed all that, giving supreme dominance especially to the six nuclear powers, the USA, Russia, China, England, France, and now also Pakistan (not counting Israel and North Korea as ambivalent entities in this arms race).

Whether the European Union will witness a consolidation and merging of forces to make it to a future superpower certainly remains to be seen, and this particularly in light of the Russian war against Ukraine since 2022, which is strongly supported by western Europe (Rollinger, Posselt, Klinkott, and Ruffing, eds., 2026) being afraid of further Russian desires to recapture other lands previously under the control of the Soviet Union until 1991. Altogether, it makes good sense to investigate European history, culture, religion, and the arts all by themselves (Oschema 2013) before we take into account a multiplicity of influences, exchanges, or translations, mostly from East to West. As Andreas Hellerstedt now claims, the quest for ethics, derived from classical Roman and Greek cultures, could be identified as the most central cultural feature characterizing this continent at least until the twentieth century (Hellerstedt 2018). However, postmodern cynicism, the realization of the absurd nature of human existence, and the deep fear of the current revolution in computer technology (AI, robotization, mechanization, automation, etc.) appear to have made us rather suspicious of the quest itself because we no longer know for sure who has put us on the path for an uncertain goal and whether it is really worth pursuing it in the future. It could well be, as some people might aver, that the concept of the quest constitutes nothing but a narrative strategy to make people feel comfortable with their existence, providing them with a certain sense of idealism, blinding us all hence to the actual economic and political power structures. But this is beyond the scope of this paper.

The Quest as a Literary Motif

Literary studies, above all, can help us exceedingly well to come to terms with the history of mentality and thus to track down some of the key strategies that we would identify as common denominators characteristic of that continent throughout the ages (Dinzelbacher, ed. 2008). Here we discover expressions of fear, anger, hatred, happiness, love, worry about death, longing for the divine, reflections about the relationship between humans and nature, and of the sense of time. All those aspects critically determine culture, hence, the expressions of those sentiments in narrative works serve in turn to determine people's perceptions or attitudes. Although we are hence dealing only with fictional projections, those can profoundly illuminate commonly shared values that influenced, drove, and directed a pan-European culture at least in the pre-modern period. After all, poets reflect common notions, address wider audiences, communicate with the public, are charged with composing certain types of songs or narratives, to elaborate specific values and ideals, to educate younger listeners/readers, and are at the same time influenced by their sources. We are thus dealing with the most fascinating phenomenon of poetry being a mirror of society and concomitantly influencing the social and cultural conditions.

Previous scholars have relied heavily on the notion of the myth and the hero's journey (Joseph Campbell 1949; Claude Luttrell 1974; Northrop Frye 1976) to identify the archetypal elements in world literature (for brief introductions, see, for instance, <https://literariness.org/2025/05/13/the-quest-in-literature/>; <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quest>). Of course, if we consider DNA data and the results of ancient archaeology and then reflect on the interactions among the various peoples living in the wider Mediterranean, the concept of 'Europe' might be somewhat problematic, as Josephine Crawley Quinn has recently argued somewhat polemically (Quinn 2024). Even though we could agree with her that the early history of the Greek and Roman civilizations were the results of extensive exchanges with and influences from the Phoenicians, Egyptians, or Babylonians, these Western powers nevertheless emerged as unique cultural entities clearly separate from neighboring civilizations.

In many of those debates concerning Europe's identity, unfortunately, especially late antique, medieval, and early modern literatures have been mostly ignored although we can identify that long period of ca. 1500 years as the furnace in which the modern European notion of the quest was forged (cf. at least Ropa 2014). European travel writing since the early Middle Ages mirrored this universal desire to expand one's perspectives and reach new lands, whether we think of the Icelandic sagas, courtly romances, late medieval pilgrimage accounts, or travelogues (see now the contributions to Sobeki, ed., 2025).

Hence, if we want to identify and analyze a characteristic European element consistently pursued throughout the ages, we can profitably rely on the history of literature as a reflection of dominant topics, concerns, interests, themes, and motifs. For instance, heroic poetry, courtly romances, courtly love poetry, fable narratives, hagiographical accounts, or erotic verse narratives were commonly shared across the continent, irrespective of whether they originated from non-European cultures or not. Of course, it makes good sense to pursue a global perspective as much as possible, but we really ought to consider first of all common values, concerns, and topics as discussed among the various continental audiences before we turn our attention outside as a second hermeneutic step. That initial task itself proves to be formidable since we are dealing with roughly one thousand and five hundred years of European literature and history. Only a book-length study could do full justice to this topic, so here I limit myself to the motif of the quest as it appears in many different texts from late antiquity to the late sixteenth century and will study exemplary cases confirming the consistent use of this motif in medieval and early modern continental literature (for a specialized study pertaining to the quest for Arcadia, see Holberton 2022, for the quest motif in medieval Italian literature, see Kleinhenz 1994).

The Quest as a Unique Issue in Pre-Modern European Literature

Undoubtedly, virtually every literary text is embedded in a wider intertextual network, which can easily be traced across languages, religions, cultures, and political structures. As recent theoretical and pragmatic studies have illustrated, a more comprehensive interpretation always ought to take into consideration the

relevant sources a poet drew from. Both the Christian Scriptures and classical literature have always constituted the bedrock of European literature, whether within the framework of the Catholic Church or the Greek-Orthodox Church (Curtius 1990). To do justice to the demands of thorough and profound critical discussions of any literary text, we have to accept the constant presence of intertextuality and the history of reception as fundamental principles regularly at work (Classen 2025a; Classen 2025b).

Naturally, this observation requires an intensive and inclusive study program which can be accomplished only after many years of reading and analysis (again, for the most seminal and far-reaching research in that regard, see Curtius 1990; cf. also Auerbach 1964). Nevertheless, a comparative study makes it possible to recognize shared structures, symbols, motifs, and themes. The intent here thus consists of identifying the extent to which the notion of the quest or the journey through life can be isolated as a characteristic feature of European literature at least since late antiquity (for the concept of the quest in modern literature, see Borg Cardona 2023; for the epistemological quest in medieval literature, see Classen 2008a).

The quest entails that an individual, a hero, is driven to accomplish a certain goal, to achieve personal triumphs, and to realize in that process specific ideals that then can serve the members of the audience as models to replicate or imitate. The quest might, of course, be a universal or global topic, which future studies would have to examine on a much broader level than can be realized here. With quest, however, I do not mean a simple pursuit of some material concepts, such as wealth, power, and physical well-being. The true and ultimate goal should be, for instance, happiness in its esoteric dimensions, as outlined already by the late Roman philosopher Boethius in his seminal treatise *De consolazione philosophiae* (ca. 524) (for a recent edition and German translation, see Gruber 2020; for the most recent critical commentary in English, see Wiitala, ed., 2024). As he had argued convincingly, only when the individual can liberate him/herself from the workings of Fortune (Wheel of Fortune), would s/he become free to pursue the true path toward happiness, i.e., progress in the quest.

It would go too far in the present context to discuss this treatise more in detail, especially because Boethius engages with profound philosophical and theological issues combining those with the mundane experiences of people and lifting the entire discourse to a higher level where the focus then rests on whether evil even exists, on the question of free will, and God's omnipresence. However, for our purposes, we can specifically identify *De consolazione philosophiae* as a foundational text that has influenced all of Western literature ever since through countless translations into many different vernaculars, editions, and adaptations both in text and image (see the contributions to Gleib, Kaminski, and Lebsanft, ed., 2010; Kaylor, Noel Harold Jr. and Philip Edward Phillips, eds. 2012; Kaylor, Noel Harold Jr. and Philip Edward Phillips, eds. 2016).

Only once the protagonist has learned his lessons from the allegorical figure of Philosophy, which proves to be difficult for him – and for us as the readers – does he find himself on the right path to pursue his quest toward true happiness. We recognize here the basis of all Western attempts to overcome the constraints of the material prison people find themselves in and to reach a higher objective in their lives. Once, when the individual understands the true goal of his/her quest and embarks on it does s/he live out the potentials of life and strives toward an ultimate purpose that gives meaning to existence.

The obvious parallels to similar strategies and ideals in Buddhism, Islam, Judaism, or Hinduism cannot be denied, but within our context, we can certainly recognize in Boethius's treatise one of the most far-reaching philosophical treatises determining European thinking, attitudes, morality, and ethics ever since, especially because Boethius operated exclusively in a logical and argumentative manner, leaving out religious perspectives despite the constant reference to the *summum bonum*, the absolute Good, or hence God Himself. What matters here is not any divine help to improve people's lives, but, instead, the rational realization of the deceptive nature of all good fortune and the truth resting beyond the Wheel of Fortune. Not surprisingly, *De consolazione philosophiae* became one of the foundational texts studied in all European schools and universities far into the nineteenth century, and it remains most insightful and illuminating until today.

The enormously impactful history of reception of *De consolatioe philosophiae* hence confirms that here we can recognize the intellectual launch of the timeless concept of the quest at least in theoretical terms, here understood within an intellectual framework, which subsequent philosophers, poets, artists, composers, and then also medical and early modern authors and architects were to pursue in and through their works.

The Quest in Vernacular Literature: A European Perspective

Apollonius of Tyre and Floris and Blancheflour

Although medieval Europe was deeply determined by Latin culture, as promoted by the Catholic Church and the advanced educational institutions (since the twelfth century: universities above all), the vernacular soon made its presence heard, so from early on, we recognize the emergent interest in the motif of the quest, as perhaps most dramatically illustrated by the Old English heroic epic *Beowulf* (ca. 750 C.E.). The Swedish warrior arrives in Denmark to save the local king from the cannibalistic Grendel and then the latter's mother, both horrible monsters that no one can defeat except for Beowulf. Indeed, he succeeds in killing both, after which he returns home, where he then rules successfully as the leader of his people for fifty years when even he faces a challenge beyond his physical prowess, a dragon. With the help of his retainer Wiglaf, Beowulf can kill that monster as well, but he succumbs to the poison that rages through his body once he has been bitten by the dragon.

There are many different approaches to this heroic epic poem, but we can be certain that it profoundly mirrored the idea of the quest, even at the cost of giving one's life in that pursuit. We observe a somewhat happier outcome of the quest in the medieval Latin *Waltharius* (tenth century), but in the Middle High German *Nibelungenlied* (ca. 1200), all efforts fail to establish peaceful relationships between the various powers (the Icelandic Queen Brunhild, the Netherlandish hero Siegfried, and the liminal figure, the seneschal Hagen serving at the Burgundian court). Following Brunhild's deception and ultimate rape by Siegfried, the latter is murdered by Hagen, which then leads Siegfried's widow Kriemhild to seek revenge. Tragically, the consequence of her actions then consists of the death of all Burgundians and Huns, even Kriemhild is killed (for solid discussions of the genre of heroic poetry, see the contributions to Konstans and Raaflaub, eds., 2010).

One of the earliest examples of the quest motif, however, can be tracked down to the anonymous *Apollonius of Tyre*, originally composed either in the second or the third century probably in Greek but certainly soon rendered into Latin (Archibald 1991). It quickly turned into one of the most successful pan-European bestsellers, to use an anachronistic term. Countless translators and adaptors worked with this prose romance well into the early seventeenth century. In fact, it easily proves to be highly popular even among contemporary readers, such as college students studying medieval literature as personal experiences have regularly confirmed.

One of the key topics addressed by this anonymous work easily proves to be the quest, or rather a multiplicity of diverse quests, with the protagonist suffering from various strikes of misfortune and fortune. Nevertheless, he struggles hard to survive and is actually successful for a long time until he is badly deceived regarding his daughter's alleged death. Having lost already his wife when she had seemingly died due to medical complications during the delivery of their baby, Apollonius finally breaks down when the epitaph on his daughter's tomb announces that she had passed away. Subsequently, Apollonius roams the Eastern Mediterranean without any further goal in his life, deeply depressed, having lost any desire to pursue his existence because there is no longer any quest waiting for him.

In reality, his daughter Tarsia had only been kidnapped by pirates just before she was supposed to have been murdered. The pirates sold her into slavery. She was bought by a pimp to work in his brothel, but she could always move her suitors to pity through her words when she tells them her life's tragedy and sheds bitter tears. Everyone is greatly impressed by her rhetorical skills, so when Apollonius happens to arrive in the harbor of Mytilene where the young woman suffers, she is sent to the almost suicidal man to relieve him of his depression. Both delight each other with riddles, but at the end, she collapses, being

completely frustrated and despondent about the strange man's rejection of her. She tells the tragedy of her life, which then finally reveals her true identity. This then resolves all conflicts because Apollonius recognizes and embraces his daughter. He also discovers his wife and can return with both back home. Subsequently, all culprits, including the pimp and Tarsia's foster mother, Dionysia, who had ordered a servant to kill her, are executed. Tarsia happily marries the prince of Mytilene who had treated her so well and had arranged her visit to the man in the hold of his ship, i.e., her father.

What does the quest ultimately consist of upon which the entire narrative is based? First, Apollonius pursues truth, solving King Antiochus's riddle which he had created to hide his incestuous relationship with his daughter from the world. Then, he struggles to recover from his shipwreck and finds love. Thereupon, however, he loses first his wife, then, years later, his daughter, and finally he himself is caught in hopeless desperation and depression. But the goal remains the same, and it is accomplished at the end, with the entire family being reunited, the daughter being happily married, and the parent generation living a happy life together after their reunion. The evil king who had raped his own daughter is killed, so goodness succeeds and the goal is ultimately achieved.

One of the main themes throughout the text proves to be the effort to read inscriptions properly and thus to detect truth, just as the theme of the riddles challenges the individual and forces him/her to pursue an intellectual quest. Apollonius is most eager to solve the king's riddle, and to verify his solution, but the king then proscribes him, which sets Apollonius on a life-long quest/journey with many ups and downs. However, as we observe throughout, intelligence, erudition, and wisdom gain the upper hand and allow him and his family to come together again to enjoy a happy and fulfilled life.

As the example of the two medical doctors in Ephesus confirms, who examine the body of the seemingly dead woman, with each one reaching a very different conclusion, the critical task always consists of analyzing the world carefully, to decipher the signals – the seemingly dead woman is still breathing – and to provide all the help possible to retrieve her from virtually certain death. Both the young physician and Apollonius prove to be similar in their intellectual approach, and young Tarsia demonstrates that honesty, empathy, and loyalty, expressed through her words and her tears, can and should lead the way toward truth (Classen 2008b).

The Wheel of Fortune exerts tremendous influence, tossing the protagonist from life to death and then back to life, from happiness and joy to complete frustration and sadness, and back again. The overarching quest pursued by father and daughter proves to be the path through life to protect themselves as much as possible from devastation and death, and to recover happiness and meaning after all. The anonymous poet composed his narrative a long time before Boethius wrote his famous treatise *De consolazione philosophiae*, and he antedated in many ways his notion of the true path toward happiness, identifying it as a quest to cope with shipwreck, the loss of family members, and intellectual challenges as keys to happiness in life.

Floris and Blancheflour

Either before the emergence of the courtly romance with King Arthur and the Round Table in the twelfth century or concomitantly, aristocratic audiences became familiar with another pan-European narrative which exerted tremendous influence across languages far into the early modern age. The earliest version, the Old French *Floire et Blancheflor* (ca. 1160), was soon translated into many different vernaculars because its central themes exerted universal interests fundamentally associated with the global conflict between the Christian and Muslim world, in this case, the Reconquista of the Iberian Peninsula. The essential plot sets in when the Muslim ruler, Felix of al-Andalus, attacks Galicia and defeats a group of pilgrims, taking one Christian woman, wife of a slain knight who had opposed the enemies, as a slave to serve as a maid for his wife. Both women are pregnant and deliver their respective child on the same day, Floire and Blancheflor, or Floris and Blancheflour in the Middle English version.

Both children are raised together and from very early on fall in love with each other, which deeply worries his parents because the Christian girl is not worthy for their son. They try everything they can think of to prevent any further emotional development because they do not want Floris to bond with the slave

woman's daughter. While they have sent him away for educational purposes, they sell the girl to merchants who take her as a slave to the emperor of Babylon. When Floris returns and is told that she had died, as allegedly confirmed by an epitaph on her tomb, he is so sad that he wants to commit suicide. His mother realizes the imminent danger, so she reveals the truth to her son. Floris is immediately resolved to follow his beloved and goes on his quest, which emerges hence as a significant parallel theme compared with *Apollonius*, and as a foundation for countless other quest narratives in the high and late Middle Ages (for an English translation, see Broughton, trans., 1966; for global discussions of the Spanish and the European tradition, see Grieve 1997; for the German version by Konrad Fleck, see Putzo 2015).

Floris learns that Babylonian merchants have purchased the young woman, so he embarks on his own journey, a quest driven by his strong erotic desires to be reunified with his beloved. He has to overcome numerous challenges and masters them all well due to his high level of intellect, bravery, and courage. Nevertheless, when he and Blancheflour are eventually discovered and supposed to be executed, they display such a strong sense of love for each other that everyone at the Emir's court is moved to tears. Even the tyrannical ruler recognizes and acknowledges the purity of the two young people's love for each other. Deeply moved, he allows them to marry, and he takes Blancheflour's female friend, Clarice, as his wife. Subsequently, word reaches Floris that his father has died, so he returns home with Blancheflour and ascends to the throne, which allows him to convert all his people to Christianity.

Behind all the narrative ups and downs, the poet outlined the specific elements of a quest. The two young people are firmly bonded through love, and they cannot live without the other, a theme which will be paralleled only slightly later by the many *Tristan* romances from across Europe, especially Gottfried von Strassburg's *Tristan and Isolde* (ca. 1210). But *Floris and Blancheflour* seems to have originated in the vicinity of Northern Spanish courts where the Christian knights were deeply committed to reconquering the rest of the Iberian Peninsula – the Reconquista. The *Tristan* romances reached the Continent from the British Isles, by contrast, and were not concerned with the religious conflicts and the problem of slavery.

By contrast, both in *Apollonius* and in *Floris*, the female protagonist is sold into enforced prostitution, but both times, she is rescued in time and can preserve her chastity, honor, and dignity. While in the older text, Tarsia then marries the prince of Mytilene after she and her father have been reunified, in *Floris*, the young man manages to track her down his beloved in the distant land of Babylon where he demonstrate so powerfully his profound love for Blancheflour that his actions mellow the hearts and minds of the ruler and his people. This pure love, this complete commitment to the quest to recover the beloved, and the willingness of both lovers to sacrifice him/herself for the other to save the other person's life humanize the foreign court (*Floris*) and the Mediterranean city (*Apollonius*). Personal happiness, peace, justice, tolerance, and basic respect for the other members of society emerge from this experience, which signals that the quest itself was recognized as the critical tool to transform humanity and to improve society in ethical and moral terms.

The Quest in Courtly Romances

Both Chrétien de Troyes and Hartmann von Aue would deserve full recognition as the founders of the quest romance. The former introduced the genre to twelfth-century aristocratic courts in France, and the latter transferred the concept to German audiences. King Arthur resides over the Round Table, and there are constantly new challenges which the individual hero takes up, meets head-on, might win, but then loses again in a different context, only to regain the upper hand or recovering from his previous defeat to triumph after all. In countless iterations, the courtly hero needs to go through the various stages in his life in order to accomplish his quest, Research has already examined the various romances, so it would be redundant to go into detail here. All that matters here is the realization that the model gained global relevance across the continent and determined aristocratic culture far into the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries. But we could focus on a short verse narrative by Hartmann where the notion of the quest gains existential relevance, his "Der arme Heinrich" (ca. 1190; Lord Henry), which finds virtually no parallels

in medieval or early modern literature (for a solid English translation, see Tobin, Vivian, and Lawson, trans., 2001).

The protagonist, Prince Heinrich, enjoys his life to the fullest when he is suddenly struck by leprosy, at that time certainly a deadly disease. Indeed, when Henry consults with a doctor in Montpellier, he receives bad news; there is no help for him; he would certainly die soon. But the young man does not yet give up and consults with another doctor, this one in Salerno near Naples. This time, although the medical conclusion is the same, the doctor knows of a magical solution, if Henry would find a nubile virgin willing to give her blood for him. Her life would hence save his own, a striking contradiction to the Hippocratic oath which was also observed in the Middle Ages. Moreover, once Henry has actually found such a willing victim, we face yet another ethical conflict because such a woman would hence commit suicide, one of the worst sins severely condemned by the Church.

Nevertheless, once the protagonist has revealed his medical history as outlined by the doctor in Salerno to his host, a peasant family, their daughter, who has deep compassion for him, if it is not strong love, declares her readiness to sacrifice herself for the lord. Although she is still very young, her enormous rhetorical skill overwhelms both her parents and Henry, and later also the medical doctor, so the two finally travel to southern Italy where the surgical operation is supposed to take place. Henry's quest at this point consists of nothing but the desire to live, i.e., to recover his health. However, he does not understand the consequences of his own actions and is about to destroy voluntarily what soon proves to be the most valuable aspect in his existence, the love of this young woman.

As the entire verse narrative signals, the protagonist finds himself on the wrong track in his life, especially because he is willing at the end to sacrifice the life of the beautiful and chaste young girl so that he can overcome his leprosy. Just before she is to die, with her heart cut out by the surgeon, Henry has a chance to gaze through a crack in the door into the interior, where he suddenly sees her lying on the operation table. This brief moment turns into an epiphany for him, since he realizes that the true beauty and value, i.e., his soul, rests inside, whereas the outside, his sick and dying body, is located outside. In the last moment, he interrupts the doctor, prevents him from killing the beautiful victim, and accepts his own mortality.

Miraculously, this transformation of his mind is then recognized by God ("the speculator cordis") who then grants Henry his physical healing because he has suddenly been granted a look into his own soul, so to speak, which was the actual being in danger of dying. Leprosy is here identified as a metaphor, and the young woman/girl thus turns out to be a symbol of his soul. Having returned home, healthy and well again, he hence marries her, with all his friends' full approval, and this thus restores the spiritual completion with body and soul joining their forces once again (Duckworth 1996).

Hartmann here presents a complex case of a quest which at first proves to be exclusively driven by the protagonist's desire to survive his leprosy and to regain his physical health. The real quest, however, should have consisted of searching for his spiritual health, which he manages to do only at the end when his 'soul' is about to be killed by the physician. The problem addressed by the poet consists of the question of how the individual can recognize in time what the right path through his/her life might be and how to identify the goal of the quest that makes one's life worthwhile and meaningful.

Wolfram von Eschenbach and Dante Alighieri

Although rarely if ever done, it is worth reading Wolfram von Eschenbach's *Parzival* (ca. 1205) in conjunction with Dante Alighieri's *Divina Commedia* (completed ca. 1320) because in both literary works we can recognize the shared motif of the quest. Young Parzival is the designated successor to the Grail kingdom where chaos rules, but he does not understand the principles governing that mysterious realm and so fails to ask the decisive question when he is granted early on entrance to this sacred space (Kennedy 2009). Hence, he is expelled, not knowing fully what has happened to him, but from then on

he has to embark on a long quest until he has reached the necessary maturity to be invited back to the Grail and to redeem and relieve the suffering King Anfortas.

There is no quest without fundamental challenges, and we can identify the same phenomenon in Dante Alighieri's *Divina Commedia* where the pilgrim Dante is in critical need of guides, primarily Virgil who takes him through Inferno, St. Bernard on his subsequent steps, and ultimately his beloved Beatrice, who welcomes him in Paradiso and from there takes him to the Empyrian. It would not help us much to attempt a comparative analysis of both masterpieces, but we can be certain that both are determined by the protagonist's quest in the spiritual world. Even though Parzival does not enter heaven or paradise, he assumes the throne of the Grail which supersedes the realm of King Arthur. Throughout his long journey, Parzival is always filled with strong feelings of love for his wife, Condwiramurs, but he is allowed to welcome her back only once he has accomplished his task. Similarly, Dante the pilgrim is inspired by his love for Beatrice but has to wait until he has reached Paradiso. Beyond that, we might not find too many other parallels, apart from the fundamental and shared idea of the quest that takes the individual from his earthly and material conditions into another dimension.

Dante pursued a deeply religious quest, whereas Parzival is bound by his knightly hence ethical ideals. Almost as in the case of the Old English poem *Beowulf*, divine intervention is needed for the questing protagonist to overcome the earthly challenges and thus to prepare himself for the ultimate task, which allows him to restore happiness in this world. Of course, Beowulf suffers his death, which signals a certain degree of failure, and his retainers thus grieve deeply the loss of their leader. Nevertheless, even this Old English hero accomplished his ultimate goal, even though he had to give his life for this final triumph. This is not the same in the case of Parzival, who is gracefully welcomed by the Grail, calmly asks the decisive question, and can thus redeem the Grail itself, which restores harmony and order in this world. *Beowulf* concludes rather ominously, where Dante's *Divina Commedia* reaches the pilgrim's apogee once Beatrice has taken him to the inner sanctum of the divine.

The quest itself determines the protagonist's path, irrespective of the price that has to be paid on the way, such as in *Waltharius* or the *Chanson de Roland*. Parallel aspects can be easily identified in the Icelandic *Njáls Saga* and in the Old Spanish *El Poema de Mío Cid*, all of which are determined by the principle notion of the quest, which takes the individual protagonist from the ground level to the pinnacle in his life irrespective of the painful experiences on the way.

The Quest for Honor and Human Failure: The Circuitous Quest

One of the most intriguing late medieval English romances, the alliterative *Sir Gawain and the Green Knight* (ca. 1381), although having survived in only one manuscript (BL, Cotton Nero A.x), has attracted much scholarly attention, but it has not yet been fully read within the context of the hero's quest. The protagonist has to seek out the Green Chapel where he must submit under the Green Knight who has the right, according to their wager, to strike an axe at him and to decapitate him. Gawain had done the same thing to the Green Knight back home at King Arthur's court upon the stranger's own invitation, but the latter had survived by means of magic. Gawain does not command such magic and is simply afraid of dying, and yet he lives up to his promise and seeks out his opponent without any real hope of surviving this deadly game (the body of scholarship on this poem is huge, but see, for the latest efforts, Breeze 2023; Nelson Couch and Bell 2025).

Gawain embarks on his path to find the Green Knight because his honor obliges him to do so. Of course, he has no idea where to look for him, but the seeker normally does not know the specific direction or orientation and has to figure out the correct way where the true challenges await him/her, as we already know from *Apollonius* and *Floris*; Parzival and Dante also needed a guide or a call from the Grail itself to recover the way toward the inner sanctum. Gawain, however, goes through a very complex labyrinth of character testing before he finally faces the Green Knight, but he has already failed when he eventually reaches the Green Chapel. Without going too much into detail, he had accepted a magical belt (sash) from the lady of the house who is trying to seduce him. According to the wager with the lord of the

castle, he was supposed to turn it over to him as his trophy from that day, while he would receive the lord's prey he had hunted in the forest. But Gawain, hoping that the belt might save his life, hides it, which thus constitutes the decisive infraction.

The lord of the castle, Bertilak of Hautdesert, of course, turns out to be the Green Knight, and he only wanted to test Gawain's steadfastness and thus the entire Arthurian company. As a punishment for his small infraction, he nicks his neck when swinging the axe at him, but he does not hurt him otherwise. Instead, he laughs about the entire situation, expresses his understanding of Gawain's secretive action, and invites him back to his castle because everything had only been part of his 'game' he had played with the court of King Arthur to test their valor and steadfastness (as to play, game, and leisure in the Middle Ages from a historical perspectives, see Milliman, ed., 2024; for additional approaches, see the contributions to Classen, ed., 2019).

However, for Gawain, this outcome represents shameful, as he later reveals to the entire Arthurian court, but the king and his knights only laugh with great empathy for Gawain and consider his actions as not blameworthy. Instead, he had only demonstrated his human character, desiring with all his might to survive this horrible decapitation game. Subsequently they all decide to wear from then on a green belt which represents their public manifestation of their humility in face of a powerful destiny they cannot control. For them, Gawain had completed his quest successfully, despite his small failure not to hand over the green belt because he had simply wanted to survive the deadly challenge. In short, Gawain accomplished his goal, superseding them all, and because of his small infraction, he had also proven to be one of them. Their shared laughter at the end signals their collective relief that their lives have been spared, while Gawain had risked his own to preserve all of their honor.

His journey consists of a circular movement in spatial terms, but it is a quest to find himself, to reconfirm the courtly and knightly values, and to prove that the realm of King Arthur indeed lives up to its expectations. Of course, he himself failed by not having turned over the belt to Bertilak as part of their agreement, but even the latter simply laughs it off because he fully understands and empathizes with his guest, acknowledging that this infraction was simply the result of his human condition, the desire to live and to survive an impossible decapitation game (for the history of laughter, see now the contributions to Bayless, ed., 2020). As much as Gawain proves to be humiliated, he actually redeemed himself fully, as the Arthurian company fully acknowledges, especially because they then all wear a green girdle as a sign of their complete approval and support of the best knight among their Round Table. The quest has been achieved, and happiness thus returns to the court.

Clouding-Over of the Quest and New Social and Scientific Challenges of the Quest in the Early Modern Age

The motif of the quest has continued to be of greatest relevance in Western literature, whether it was determined by religious or scientific values. The goals of the quest have certainly differed from writer to another writer, from period to another period, but the desire to learn, to grow, to understand, to recognize, to perceive, and to transcend the material limitations has stayed with us throughout the ages. We could easily refer to the great tradition of medieval mystics, of the large movement of spiritualists, of Enlightenment thinkers and poets, of the Romantic quest for deeper truth and identity, or of the influential schools of Realists and Naturalists in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries.

It might be a profound question whether European authors and poets are still occupied with the issue of the quest, or whether cynicism and fatalism have robbed of this original desire to go on a quest to achieve ineffable, transcendental, or religious goals. Of course, most individuals today pursue education, look for jobs, establish families, build their lives, and the like, all of which can certainly be subsumed under the notion of the quest. But it seems doubtful whether the grand ideas of the quest as we find them in late antiquity and the Middle Ages have survived the sobering experiences in the first half of the twentieth century with WWI and WWII, along with the Holocaust, not even considering the many genocides that have been committed already since the early twentieth century.

This criticism, the raising of doubt about the loftiness of the concept of the quest, can already be identified since the early sixteenth century, if we can trust two major texts published then, first the anonymous *Fortunatus* (1509), and then the *Historia von D. Johann Fausten* (1587) (both contained in the edition by Müller 1990). While the protagonist in the first novel aims for the exploration of all of Europe and later also of the Middle East, the protagonist in the second one desires to learn the deepest secrets here in life and thus signs a pact with the devil. Although this allows him to enjoy his life to the fullest extent, ultimately, he becomes a victim of the devil who rips his body apart and takes his soul. The enormous popularity of these two texts and their authors' attempt to outline the respective protagonists' entire life can be taken as constitutive of the rise of the early modern German novel (Classen 2026). But in both cases, the quest, though determined by different goals, does not yield the expected outcome, and failure if not a catastrophe concludes both works. The motif of the quest continued to be relevant in Western European literature ever since, but it turned into a highly risky enterprise, as both *Fortunatus* and *Faustus* have to realize rather painfully.

In the first case, the young protagonist faces severe threats to his life but manages to survive until he is lucky enough to receive a miraculous money purse that never becomes empty. *Fortunatus* uses his endless wealth primarily for traveling across the entire continent and later also into the Asian East, but dangers continue to threaten him. He is even fortunate enough to acquire, by means of theft, a magical cap that allows him to travel to wherever he wants to get within seconds. And with his money, he can basically 'buy' as his bride the daughter of an impoverished count and thus establish himself as a high-ranking member of Cypriot society.

However, the future quickly turns into a horrible quagmire, at least for his two sons. The younger one, Andolosia, misuses the magical objects against his father's explicit instructions formulated before his death, and so he has to undergo many difficult adventures. Finally, two jealous courtiers kidnap him and torture him to death because they want to find out the origin of all his money. The older brother, Ampedo, dies out of grief over the disappearance of his brother, so the young dynasty has already reached its end. The author still reveals the great fascination with money, but he clearly outlines the implied dangers and the horrible consequences when money is not coupled with ethics and morality. *Fortunatus* himself does not have to witness anything of that due to his death, but he himself had faced enough threats to his life during his many travels. It also remains uncertain what he might have profited from his extensive travels since he does not translate his experiences into any specific actions or teachings. Even his final warning about the risks involved with the money purse and the travel cap has no impact, so destiny takes its course leading to the two sons' rather miserable or pathetic death. Undoubtedly, the anonymous author drew from the classical and medieval notion of the quest, but since the protagonists are no longer driven by philosophical, ethical, religious, or moral ideals and only think of the material joys which money can grant, the quest ultimately comes to a crushing end (for the best literary-historical analysis, see Kästner 1990; cf. now also Kiening 2021).

In the case of the *Historia von D. Johann Fausten*, the protagonist desires to gain deep knowledge and thus to compete with God. But this is only possible with the help of the devil, and the latter ultimately deceives *Faustus* and takes his soul with him because he does not succeed in protecting himself in religious terms and does not seek help from God in the last moment. Early modern science becomes here the target of the poet's criticism, and we find the same perspective more or less mirrored in the much later versions of the same literary source, that is, Goethe's *Faust* (Part I, 1808; Part II, 1832) and Thomas Mann's *Dr. Faustus* (1947) (for a brief overview of the history of reception, see <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Faust-literary-character>).

Ironically, the desire for the quest has thus continued until the present, but the optimism in its successful conclusion or realization rather soured already in the early modern age. The desire for accomplishing one's life's goal never disappeared and is certainly with us today as well if we think, for instance, of the countless modern novels that earned the Nobel Prize for Literature, such as Hermann Hesse's *Glasperlenspiel* from 1943, Günter Grass's *Blechtrommel* from 1959, or Christa Wolf's *Kindheitsmuster* from 1976. But already Siegfried Lenz's *Die Deutschstunde* from 1968 and Bernhard Schlink's famous novel *Der*

Vorleser from 1995 revealed that the quest was no longer achievable because the horrors of the past have caught up with the present generation. Significantly, the fear of modern technology, nuclear power, and AI have renewed the major interest in Goethe's *Faust* as a literary platform for fundamental criticism of (post-)modernity. It would be rather productive to include here also an analysis of Miguel de Cervantes's *Don Quijote* (1605 and 1615) to round off our discussion of the quest as a central European motif. But suffice it only to indicate that Cervantes profoundly ironized this ideal and signaled explicitly that an entire epoch had come to an end. The longing for the quest might not have disappeared, but it had become rather questionable, as many writers in the twentieth century confirmed in their own terms.

Conclusion

It is certainly not the ambition of this paper to analyze the entire history of German or European literature, a goal that would require multi-volume studies. Instead, the intention was more modest, to identify some of the characteristic features of European culture and literature at least in the post-Roman period, the Middle Ages, and the early modern age. As we could observe, the motif of the quest indeed assumed central importance throughout the entire continent, though here I have discussed only a handful of relevant examples. Other relevant works would be the Irish *St. Brendan* legend, mystical literature by Hildegard of Bingen or Julian of Norwich, or, as a negative example, the *Nibelungenlied*. The quest underscored the famous romance *Roman de Silence* by Heldris de Cornuälle and the famous *Roman de la rose* by Guillaume de Lorris and then, several decades later, Jean de Meun. The highly popular hagiographical text, "Le tombeor de Notre Dame" or the *chantefable* "Aucassin et Nicolette" would just as much have to be read as quest narratives as the anonymous Middle English *Pearl*. The vast corpus of *fabliaux*, *mären*, or *novelle*, or the many fables would not fall into that category because of their narrative brevity. But whenever a poet endeavored to explore his/her protagonist's course through life, the quest appears as the dominant topic, even when the circumstances often prove to be quite different.

As we have seen, the alliterative *Sir Gawain and the Green Knight* demonstrated that there was still hope left for the protagonist to achieve his goal and to return home to Arthur's court as a triumphant though subdued hero. But in the peasant satire, *Der Ring* by Heinrich Wittenwiler (ca. 1400), the protagonists' quest for happiness, love, and marriage utterly fails, and there is no hope left for the recovery of society at the end. The fifteenth century witnessed the renewed effort to restore traditional ideals, such as in Thomas Malory's *Mort d'Artur* (1485), but Fernando de Roja's *Celestina* (1499) already indicated that traditional aspirations might not be realizable because all love had become commodified. The experiences of the Thirty Years' War (1618–1648) might have been the death knell to the literary concept of the quest, as reflected in Hans Jakob Christoffel von Grimmelshausen's *Simplicius Simplicissimus* (1669), but humans always dream of a better life, so the quest for the quest has continued until today, though it appears rather frayed and tattered.

Nevertheless, despite the steady decline of the trust in this idealistic motif since the early modern age, the quest constantly experienced its renaissance in European literature since the seventeenth century. Of course, tracing the development until today, we clearly recognize a deep sense of frustration, at times even hopelessness, and yet, the quest certainly represents, as the many different examples from the pre-modern world have fully confirmed, a central feature of European culture.

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